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- 3a; Ar=4-ClC₆H₄ g; Ar=4-NCC₆H₄
 b; Ar=4-Me₂NC₆H₄ h; Ar=4-BrC₆H₄
 c; Ar=2-O₂NC₆H₄ i; Ar=4-CH₂CH₂C₆H₄
 d; Ar=3,4,5-(MeO)₃C₆H₂ j; Ar=4-OH-3-OCH₃C₆H₃
 e; Ar=3,4-Cl₂C₆H₃ k; Ar=3,4-(HO)₂C₆H₃
 f; Ar=4-i.PrC₆H₄ l; Ar=2-Br-C₆H₄

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 5-Arylidene-1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*b*]-1,2-benzisothiazol-3-one-6,6-dioxides

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HETEROCYCLES containing nitrogen and sulphur, especially derivatives of 1,2-benzisothiazole-1,1-dioxides¹ and 1,2,4-triazines² are known to exhibit biological activity. With this in view an attempt has been made to incorporate both the moieties in a single class of compounds, viz. 1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*b*]-1,2-benzisothiazol-3-one-6,6-dioxide (2) and its various arylidene derivatives (3) and to study the antibacterial activity of the latter. Compound 2 was prepared by heating 2-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-3-hydrazino-1,2-benzisothiazole-1,1-dioxide³ (1) in benzene using *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (*p*-TSA) as a catalyst. This was condensed with various substituted benzaldehydes (3a-1).

Biological screening: Compounds 3a-1 (40 mg each) were evaluated for their antibacterial activity on gram positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram negative bacteria *Salmonella typhosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Pseudomonas pyocyanse* and *Proteus vulgaris* using Ditch-plate method⁴.

The compounds (Table 1) showed no activity against *P. vulgaris*, *P. pyocyanse* and *S. dysenteriae* (except 3k, to which this organism is sensitive). *S. aureus* was sensitive to all the compounds and *S. typhosa* was sensitive to all but four compounds, viz. 3a, b, k and l.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-1*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	201	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
b	254	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S
c	150	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S
d	186	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S
e	120	69	C ₁₈ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
f	182	61	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S
g	>250	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S
h	180	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₂ S
i	145	61	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S
j	132	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S
k	200	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S
l	198	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₂ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 681 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Hitachi R-600 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Shimadzu QP-1000 spectrometer. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

Preparation of 2: A suspension of 1 (2.83 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (40 ml) containing a few crystals of *p*-TSA was refluxed for 6 h using a Dean-Stark apparatus. After removal of the calculated amount of water, the heating was discontinued, the solution cooled to room temperature and benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting white solid after cooling, was washed with hexane, (1.85 g, 78%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 45.52; H, 3.02; N, 18.00. C₉H₇N₃O₂S requires: C, 45.56; H, 2.95; N, 17.72%); ν_{max} 1 650 (CONH) and 3 380 br cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 3.4 (2H, s, CH₂) and 7.5-8.0 (4H, m, ArH).

General method for the synthesis of 3a-1: A mixture of 2 (0.0042 mol), the corresponding benzaldehyde (0.005 mol) in benzene (35 ml) and the catalyst *p*-TSA was refluxed for 5 h using Dean-

Stark assembly. It was then cooled to room temperature and left overnight. The resulting solid was washed with hexane and recrystallised from benzene, (0.98 g, 65%), m.p. 201°; ν_{\max} 1 620 (CONH) and 3 380 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.2–7.9 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.6 (1H, s, =CH); m/z 360 (M^+).

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Triazoloquinazolines. Part-2. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 2-(2'-N-Acetyl-N-phenyl-4'-thiazolyl)-s-triazolo[1,5-c]quinazolines

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THE reported literature method¹ involving the oxidation of 4-quinazolinyldiazones by Br₂ in acetic acid gave a mixture of s-triazolo[4,3-c] and [1,5-c]quinazolines. Hence we followed an alternative route to yield exclusively one product, viz. s-triazolo[1,5-c]quinazolines by oxidising the intermediate 4-quinazolinyldiazones (2) with lead tetraacetate in acetic acid. By this hitherto unreported method we could achieve in the isolation of a single isomer with improved yields (Scheme 1, Table 1).

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian instrument (300 MHz). 4-Quinazolinyldiazones and 4-formyl-2-(N-acetyl-N-phenyl-2,5-dichlorophenyl)thiazole were synthesised by reported method².

4-Quinazolinyldiazones (2): Equimolecular quantities of 4-quinazolinyldiazones and thiazole aldehydes were refluxed in methanol for 2 h. The resulting solids were recrystallised from methanol.

Scheme 1

2-(2'-N-Acetyl-N-phenyl-4'-thiazolyl)-s-triazolo[1,5-c]quinazolines (3e): To 4-quinazolinyldiazones (2; 0.47 g, 0.00103 mol) suspended in glacial acetic acid (25 cm³) was added lead tetraacetate (0.6 g, 0.001337 mol) under stirring. After 30 min, the reaction mixture became clear and slowly a solid separated out. The stirring was continued further for 3 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from acetic acid, (0.25 g), m.p. 318°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 680 (N-Ac), 1 620, 1 590, 1 560 and 1 510 cm^{-1} (ArH); m/z 454 and 456 (M^+); δ 2.05 (3H, s, NCOCH₃), 8.2 (1H, s, (a)), 8.48 (1H, m, *o*- and *m*-coupling extreme lowfield (b)), 7.76 (1H, m, 2-*o*-couplings and adjacent to quinazoline ring (c)), 7.96 (1H, m, 2-*o*-couplings each having *m*-coupling (d)), 7.82 (1H, m, *o*-coupling with *m*-coupling merged with other signals (e)), 7.86 (1H, s, (f)), 8.1 (1H, dd, (g₁)), 8.09 (1H, d, (g₂)) and 7.88 (1H, s, (h)).

3e

Similarly, other compounds were synthesised.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield %	M p. °C
3a	H	H	CH ₃	H	47	300 ^a
3b	H	H	Cl	H	32	303 ^b
3c	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	H	Cl	50	315 ^c
3d	C ₂ H ₅	H	CH ₃	H	45	297 ^c
3e	H	Cl	H	Cl	54	318 ^a

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aacetic acid, ^bchlorobenzene, ^cdimethylformamide.